

HIPERMAT

Advanced design, monitoring, development and validation of novel
High PERFORMANCE MATERIALS and components

Deliverable 3.2. Report containing material property predictions to be used for validation of a computationally-based approach to extracting input-data for process modelling.

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2 Introduction

The HIPERMAT project aims to develop new materials or material combinations for increased lifetime of beams and rings in a hot stamping furnace, which are exposed to elevated temperatures for prolonged times. To accelerate the development process, materials and process modelling is utilized to select and optimize materials composition and processing parameters. Process simulations are a key tool for efficient implementation of additive and hybrid manufacturing processes. These simulations rely on materials property data. However, the materials data required for reliable process simulations is rarely available for a novel combination of materials and processes. In this report we outline the modeling framework employed in HIPERMAT for property predictions based on microstructure, showing examples of Laser Metal Deposition (LMD) simulation of a Ni-based superalloy. This framework forms the basis for quantifying property variation within a material specification and uncertainties in process simulations. This in turn allows to evaluate new materials for targeted performance and/or optimizing material specification to minimize batch-to-batch variability, thereby accelerating the development process for new and improved ring and beam materials in the hot stamping furnace and addressing the needs set out in HIPERMAT.

Implementation of new materials and processes in industrial production requires significant efforts beyond lab-scale prototyping and validation. Upscaling the production introduces additional process restrictions and variability, which needs to be understood and controlled to ensure consistent high-quality products. Modelling and simulations can be used to significantly reduce the experimental efforts of the upscaling process.

2.1 *The properties*

Multiphysics simulations for processes like LMD and hidrosolidification, which are considered in the HIPERMAT project, have been made possible thanks to advanced computer hardware, numerical algorithms and software. However, for the simulation results to be most relevant and useful, realistic materials properties should be adopted. These properties include:

- Liquidus and solidus temperatures
- Fraction of solidification between liquidus and solidus
- Latent heat of solidification
- Specific heat
- Density
- Thermal expansivity
- Thermal conductivity
- Surface tension of liquid
- Viscosity of liquid
- Laser absorptivity (for LMD)

These properties, in all or in part, are compiled in sources like materials handbooks, but only for some well-known materials. Furthermore, as is detailed below, properties of one material can be affected by processing, via altering its microstructure. Therefore, the incumbent data system for materials properties is an obstacle hindering reliable simulations for novel materials under novel processes.

2.2 The materials

A different set of materials as bulk materials and as thick layers applied by means of LMD are going to be developed or used:

a.-In the HIPERMAT project, the bulk materials for beams and rings are based on Grade 1.4848 and its chemically modified versions (Table 1). They have been selected based on considerations of the application conditions and how alloying would affect the microstructure and hence the properties of the materials.

Table 1. Chemical compositions of bulk materials for beams and rings. Composition differences from Grade 1.4848 are highlighted.

Element s (wt. %)	Beam Inside		Beam Entrance		Ring	Referen ce(R)	Grade 1.4848
	BEIN1	BEIN2	BEEN1	BEEN2	RI1		
	25Cr- 20Ni	25Cr- 20Ni	20Cr- 20Ni	20Cr- 25Ni	25Cr- 20Ni		
C	0.35 - 0.4	0.50 - 0.60	0.50 - 0.60	0.35 - 0.4	0.50 - 0.60	0.32	0.3 - 0.5
Si	1.5 - 2.0	1.5 - 2.0	1.5 - 2.0	1.5 - 2.0	1.5 - 2.0	1.25	1.00 - 2.50
Mn	0.8 - 1.2	0.8 - 1.2	0.8 - 1.2	0.8 - 1.2	0.8 - 1.2	1.02	2.0 max
P	0.04 max	0.033	0.040 max				
S	0.04 max	0.008	0.030 max				
Cr	24.0 - 26.0	24.0 - 26.0	18.0 - 20.0	18.0 - 20.0	24.0 - 26.0	24.6	24.0 - 27.0
Ni	20.5 - 22.0	20.5 - 22.0	20.5 - 22.0	24.0 - 26.0	20.5 - 22.0	18.2	19.0 - 22.0
Mo	0.5- 0.75	0.5- 0.75	0.5- 0.75	0.5- 0.75	0.5 - 0.75		0.5 max
Nb		0.45	0.45				
W		1.50	1.50				

b In the HIPERMAT project, the introduction of Ni-based superalloy- and high entropy alloy-based coating materials by laser metal deposition (LMD) onto an austenitic stainless steel, leads to new challenges in terms of processability and material compatibility. Process simulations are utilized in the project to identify suitable deposition parameters; however, the heat transfer analysis is highly dependent on the input materials parameters, which are typically composition-dependent and non-linear with temperature.

.b.1- The commercially available superalloy Haynes 230 (Table 2) was selected as the benchmark material for initial LMD trials within the HIPERMAT project due to its good fabricability and suitable high-temperature mechanical properties for long-term exposure to thermo-mechanical loads. It is therefore adopted to showcase the use of the “combined materials and process modeling” framework to support accelerated selection/implementation of the coating material onto the existing austenitic stainless steel used for beams/rings of the hot stamping furnace.

Table 2. A typical chemistry specification of Haynes 230, including impurity elements (Co, Fe, Cu, B, Ti)

Ni	Cr	W	Mo	Mn	Si	Al	C	La
Bal.	20.0- 24.0	13.0- 15.0	1.0- 3.0	0.3- 1.0	0.25- 0.75	0.2- 0.5	0.05- 0.015	0.005- 0.05
Co	Fe	Cu	B	Ti				
Max 5.0	Max 3.0	Max 0.5	Max 0.015	Max 0.1				

b.2- The alloy $Al_xCoCrFeNi$ ($x=0-0.2$) is a high entropy alloy (HEA) expected to exhibit good high temperature and wear properties. The Al-free version, $CoCrFeNi$ (25 at. % of each element), is austenitic (fcc structure) up to its melting point. The addition of Al introduces a B2 intermetallic phase that can contribute to yield strength and wear resistance. However, as a young material class, HEA do not enjoy the same maturity as the well-known steels and Ni-base superalloys, in terms of materials data availability.

2.3 *The approach for materials properties in HIPERMAT*

To increase the accuracy of process simulations and to evaluate the impact of chemistry variations on materials behaviors during the LMD process, the CALPHAD-based materials modeling approach is incorporated into a “combined materials and process modeling” framework. In this framework suitable LMD processing window can be identified, and the as-deposited materials properties can be predicted with the input temperature-time profiles from the LMD process simulation, which is based on the heat transfer analysis using non-linear thermodynamic properties of multicomponent alloys as predicted by the CALPHAD approach. This also applies to the simulations of casting and hydrosolidification processes.

In this report, we showcase the use of materials modelling to provide parameters for process simulations, emphasizing the importance of capturing property sensitivity to chemistry variations even within alloy specification. Further, a combined framework for materials and process modelling is outlined, including the relations between material properties and processing conditions, and the inter-dependence of material and process optimization.

3 Computational material property prediction approach for process modelling

In materials handbooks, material properties are compiled based on their alloy compositions and processing routes, with their microstructural features skipped. In contrast, the CALPHAD approach describes materials properties on the phase level, as functions of phase composition, temperature, etc. Originally, CALPHAD means parameterization of Gibbs free energy on the phase level, which enables self-consistent predictions of multi-component, multi-phase thermodynamic equilibrium via Gibbs energy minimization. Later, the CALPHAD approach has been extended to cover more phase-level attributes, such as diffusivity, molar volume (or equivalently, density), electrical and thermal conductivities. It is therefore possible to make computational predictions of materials properties fully based on microstructure.

Using a CALPHAD-based materials modelling approach, it is possible to extend upon the experimentally available data and provide properties in a wider temperature range while capturing the influence of chemistry variations on thermodynamic properties such as specific heat, liquidus and solidus temperatures and latent heat, but also physical properties such as density, thermal conductivity and liquid viscosity. Figure 1 shows a schematic of how CALPHAD-based material modelling can be used to provide necessary material parameters for process simulations.

Figure 1: Schematic of how materials modelling is used to provide input parameters for process simulations within HIPERMAT

In this section, the approach of computational material property prediction is demonstrated for the Ni-base superalloy Haynes 230, the high entropy alloy $Al_xCoCrFeNi$, and the stainless steel 1.4848.

3.1 Haynes 230

Haynes 230 is selected for the LMD process. Simulations for LMD process typically require a range of input parameters, including process parameters such as thermal and mechanical loads, and material parameters such as liquidus and solidus temperature, heat capacity and thermal conductivity. While

the process parameters to a large extent can be externally controlled by an operator, the material parameters are intrinsic to the feedstock material and typically taken from published literature or material datasheets. Even for well-studied and commercially available materials, this data is generally only available for one specific composition and process, and then only for a limited temperature range, while for new materials the data is even more scarce, if available at all.

Material datasheets for Haynes 230 contain useful data, such as the specific heat from room-temperature to 1000 °C, covering the most common application temperatures for the alloy. However, for liquid- and solid-state process simulations, a wider temperature range is needed. By calculating the specific heat (not accounting for latent heat during phase transformations) of the nominal composition of Haynes 230 (average content of all alloying elements listed in Table 2), the experimental specific heat is well-replicated in the lower temperature range. Furthermore, the available temperature range for this important material parameter is greatly extended to cover not only the solidification range, but also the high-temperature melt. Figure 2 shows the CALPHAD-predicted and datasheet values of the specific heat, respectively.

Figure 2: Predicted specific heat (not accounting for the latent heat of melting) for the nominal composition of Haynes 230, compared to the experimental data in the Haynes 230 datasheet

Another example of the usefulness of a CALPHAD-based modelling approach for material parameter determination is the sensitivity of equilibrium solidification range to alloy chemistry within the specification listed in Table 2. Possible batch-to-batch solidus and liquidus temperature variations, based on thermodynamic equilibrium calculations using Thermo-Calc software and the TCNI11 database, within the specification are shown in Figure 3. The liquidus temperature varies in a rather narrow temperature range (~20 °C) whereas the solidus temperature is highly dependent on the impurity content and varies by up to 60 °C. Other properties may vary more, or less, depending on the property and alloy specification in question. The sensitivity of material properties to small chemistry variations becomes critical when adapting conventional alloys for additive manufacturing, especially

in LMD-type processes where there is bound to be intermixing of the deposited alloy with the substrate material, causing potentially much greater chemistry variations than allowed within the specification.

Figure 3: Predicted variation of liquidus and solidus temperatures for the maximum and minimum limits of each element in the Haynes 230 alloy specification (calculations made using Thermo-Calc software and the TCNI11 database)

Additionally, the influence of processing route on the relevant material parameters (in this example the solidification range) should not be neglected, especially for manufacturing routes with rapid solidification (e.g. casting, welding, LMD/additive manufacturing), since rapid solidification causes elemental segregation in the microstructure, which in turn influences the solidification sequence and the corresponding solidification temperature range. Figure 4 shows an example of equilibrium (dotted lines) and Scheil solidification (assuming no diffusion in solids, full lines), where the Scheil solidification range for the nominal Haynes 230 composition (black) is extended by nearly 100 °C compared to the equilibrium solidification range. Additionally, the predicted influence of impurity elements on the solidification range is shown by the green (no impurity elements) and red (maximum impurity content) lines.

Figure 4: Scheil (solid) and equilibrium (dotted) solidification ranges for the nominal composition of Haynes 230 without (green), average (black) and with maximum (red) amount of impurity elements (Fe, Co, Cu, Ti, B)

Although Haynes 230 is well-studied in conventionally processed conditions, with available datasheets and handbook data, the data is only given for a typical composition and a standard heat treatment/microstructure within the alloy specification, and sometimes only as a constant value as opposed to a temperature dependent variable. Thus, material parameters for LMD simulations of the nominal Haynes 230 composition (excluding La as it is not included in the database) have been calculated using the Thermo-Calc software suite, and the associated nickel thermodynamic database (TCNI11), using a combination of equilibrium, Scheil solidification, and frozen-in equilibrium calculations to mimic the rapidly solidified microstructure of the alloy, assuming no interaction or mixing with the baseplate material. The resulting parameters are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Computationally derived materials parameters for rapidly solidified Haynes 230, using the nominal composition with no impurities, average and maximum impurity values as listed in Table 2

Property	No impurities	Average impurity content (max/2)	Maximum impurity content
Latent heat of melting (kJ/kg)	263	253	243
Solidus (°C)	1296	1203	1149
Liquidus (°C)	1398	1388	1379

3.2 High entropy alloy $Al_xCoCrFeNi$ ($x=0-0.2$)

High entropy alloy $Al_xCoCrFeNi$ ($x=0-0.2$) is another material selected for LMD coating. The properties required by LMD simulations (except laser-related properties) can be calculated using the Thermo-Calc software with the TCHEA5 database. The calculation procedure is similar to that for Haynes 230 presented above, and some selected properties are presented here.

Figure 5 shows the calculated liquidus, solidus under equilibrium, and solidus (99% solidified) under Scheil nonequilibrium solidification condition. Al addition widens solidification range (liquidus–solidus) in both conditions, but the effect is much stronger under Scheil condition (suitable for rapid solidification) than under equilibrium condition (very slow cooling). A larger solidification range usually implies a higher cracking susceptibility. On the other hand, Al addition slightly reduces liquid viscosity of this alloy.

Figure 5: Liquidus, solidus under equilibrium, and solidus under Scheil solidification condition of $Al_xCoCrFeNi$.

Figure 6: Dynamic viscosity of liquid of Al_xCoCrFeNi.

3.3 Steel 1.4848 and alternative bulk materials

Bulk materials are used in their as-cast condition. For simulations of casting and hydrosolidification, the required properties are mostly the same as required by LMD simulations, except for the laser-related properties. Among them we demonstrate viscosity and surface tension of liquid for the bulk materials, as they are important properties related to how the liquid flows in the mold and if the liquid can completely fill the mold.

Using the Thermo-Calc software with the TCFE11 database, the dynamic viscosity and surface tension of the liquid above liquidus temperature are calculated for the alloys in Table 1 (taking the median composition when there is a range). The results are presented in Figure 7. While the predicted viscosity values are quite similar among different alloys, surface tension of the modified alloys are predicted to be lower than that of the reference alloy.

Figure 7. Dynamic viscosity (left) and surface tension (right) of liquid calculated for the bulk materials

4 A demonstration of LMD simulations of Haynes 230 using computationally predicted material parameters

Using the computationally predicted materials properties as input, LMD process simulations were carried out. Figure 8 shows the temperature distribution in space, from which the size and geometry of melt pool can be visualized. Figure 9 shows the temperature history of a monitor point. It is worth noting that melt pool size and thermal history are both experimentally measurable. Therefore, the simulation results can be directly validated.

Figure 8: Example output from process simulation showing the melt pool and heat affected zone dimensions in meters during LMD deposition

Figure 9: Output temperature-time curves from process simulations. The red cross in the contour plot shows the position of the monitor point. Dimensions are shown in meters.

In addition to composition variations, differences in CALPHAD databases also lead to variations in predicted properties. Figure 10 demonstrates the calculated density and solid fraction functions for two choices of composition and CALPHAD database. Variant 1 is from Pandat database, while Variant 2 is from Thermo-Calc database TCNI11 using a different composition. The predicted properties exhibit some differences, though the general ranges and trends are in agreement.

Figure 10: Example thermo-physical property prediction variations

The variations in calculated properties result in different cooling profiles during solidification. A metric derived from the cooling profile is the so-called “cracking susceptibility coefficient” (CSC),

the ratio of time spent in the “vulnerable” interval to that in the “safe” interval. From the LMD simulations, the CSC metric can be extracted and used to represent the kinetics of solidification.

After:
 T.W. Clyne and G.J. Davies: Br. Foundryman, 1981, vol. 74, pp. 65-73.

Figure 11: A cracking susceptibility coefficient metric (left) and average values from the LMD simulations using two variants of property data (right)

The CSC is dependent on the cooling rate between liquidus and solidus. Figure 9 shows an example of the thermal behavior at an arbitrary point in the computational domain, using the Variant 1 dataset. The material undergoes multiple heating and cooling cycles as the heat source approached, processes and then moves away from that point. The LMD simulation clearly provides more information on solidification than the empirically defined CSC metric.

5 Conclusions and next steps

Material parameters are important for accurate process simulations but are rarely available for the specific composition and processing route to be simulated. Utilizing a CALPHAD-based modelling approach, it is possible to not only replicate experimentally determined material parameters, but to extend the available data to wider temperature ranges as well as capture the effects of batch-to-batch composition variations of the feedstock. Utilizing CALPHAD-based material modelling, it is thus possible to enhance the predictive capabilities of process simulations for either novel alloy compositions or to evaluate and account for the influence of batch-to-batch composition variations.

The influence of chemistry variations on hot cracking susceptibility are increasingly important when modelling the entire LMD process on a steel substrate, where mixing at the substrate/coating interface will significantly change the alloy composition. The alloy composition variation across the interface, as well as the length-scale that is affected will depend heavily on both substrate composition and alloy composition, as well as process parameters (laser power, scanning speed). Depending on the amount of alloy mixing, a different set of material parameter may be needed to provide reliable process simulations for. Similarly, if the selected alloy does not meet the property targets or the performance goals in the additively manufactured condition, the alloy composition may need to be optimized for improved as-deposited mechanical properties, or even replaced with another alternative. Any process

parameters developed for Haynes 230 or the applied high entropy alloy would then need to be re-optimized for the new alloy chemistry, which in turn would influence the as-built mechanical properties of the new alloy. This closely connected loop of alloy and process optimization, and the associated material and process modelling, can be described in a “combined material and process modelling framework”, as outlined in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Schematic view of a “combined materials and process modelling framework” and how chemistry optimization, material parameters, process optimization, thermal history and as-built properties are closely interconnected.

As the HIPERMAT project develops, and experimental results for the benchmark materials become available, the intention is to take this another step. By utilizing the optimized process parameters and the resulting simulated temperature-time profiles as input for modelling of LMD-deposited coating on a steel substrate, the alloy’s microstructure will be determined and mechanical properties predicted. This is also applicable to simulating casting and hydrosolidification. This ultimately allows for up-front evaluation of the alloy’s properties and their chemistry optimization to meet the property requirements of the final components in the hot stamping furnace.